

“Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK) followed along the fish value chain for Sustainable livelihood based Fisheries Development in Assam”

¹Ashim Kumar Borah*, ¹Sangjukta Shyam

¹National Fisheries development Board regional centre, Khanapara, Guwahati-22, Assam

***Corresponding E-mail.: akborah1980@gmail.com**

Abstract:

The State of Assam is home to numerous indigenous communities that have lived there for hundreds of years, preserving their own ways of life in all areas of their lives. Fish farmers from these communities are known for their remarkable indigenous knowledge on various indigenous methods of fish culture, fish harvesting, ecosystem conservation and management of natural resources, transportation, marketing and value addition of fish which they have assimilated over centuries through learning experiences. The state is blessed with vast and varied resources in terms of beels, rivers, reservoirs, swamps and marshes, derelict water bodies, pond and tanks with diverse indigenous fish species. From all these water resources production of 4.17 lakh MT fish was recorded in the year 2021-22 and against demand 5.08 lakh MT of fish @ 15 kg/Individual/annum, still the Production & Requirement Gap in the state is 0.91 lakh MT. With the rising demand for secure food supply due to rapid population growth and to overcome the challenges like environmental deterioration and climate changes, Indigenous Technical Knowledge (ITK) in entire fish value chain has become very much relevant in the present scenario. It is observed that from last many years farmers of the state has developed various indigenous and climate resilient technologies such as Short duration fish culture in flood prone areas of Assam, Single or Multiple stocking and multiple harvesting, Integrated fish farming with low input and high income, Use of various local tree and plant leaves for water quality management, disease prevention, long distance transportation of fish to reduce spoilage and production of various value added fishery product for enhancing domestic fish consumption. Although, fisheries sector has transformed from sustenance to knowledge based fisheries activities, still, the ITK System has lot of significance to address various key issues such as income and employment generation, poverty alleviation, judicious use of natural resources and ecological habitats.

Keywords: Indigenous Technical Knowledge, fish value chain, climate resilient technologies